

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF MODERN PRAGMALINGUISTICS: IDEAS AND PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. This article analyzes current issues of pragmatics, pragmalinguistics, and pragmatics. The philological basis is interpreted. In addition, the human factor in pragmatics has been studied in detail. Perspective indicators are highlighted.

Keywords: analyze, pragmatics, pragmalinguistics, human factor, communication strategy. communicative tactics.

Today man is at the center of all scientific fields. And linguistics in this sense is no exception. Linguists turned to the "human factor", to the native speaker - a person, a speaking person. Thus, the stage of research, which was based on formal criteria for the analysis of language, ended. Linguists have directed their interests in the field of the study of speech messages, taking into account speech impact as an important means of human communication. Increasing attention was paid to pragmatic influences, and pragmatics as a science came to the fore.

Pragmatics is an element of the "semiotic triad". Following the American researcher C.W. Morris, it is customary to divide semiotics into semantics, syntactics and pragmatics. At the same time, within the framework of semantics, CW Morris proposed to study "the relationship of signs to their objects", within the framework of syntactics - "the formal relationship of signs to each other," and pragmatics assigned the role of studying "the relationship of signs to interpreters," ie., to those "who use signs - speaking, listening, writing, reading." Pragmalinguistics is one of the directions in modern pragmatics and can be interpreted as the linguistic section of pragmatics.

Communication strategy. Communicative tactics. The totality of moves planned in advance and realized in the course of a speech act is defined as a communicative strategy. The definition of a communicative strategy depends on the goals and objectives of the study, which determine the choice of the sender of certain speech actions. Each utterance, like their sequence. performs many functions and pursues many goals, in connection with this, the speaker chooses those linguistic means that best suit them.

In the most general sense, a communication strategy includes planning the process of verbal communication depending on the specific conditions of communication and the personalities of the communicants, as well as the implementation of this plan. In other words, a communication strategy is a complex of thoughtful and motivated speech actions aimed at achieving a communicative goal. Speech actions, similar in their communicative intention, and, consequently, in semantic content, are combined into tactics subordinate to the goals of verbal communication. Communicative tactics is understood as a set of practical speech actions for the implementation of communicative intention in the real process of speech interaction. Unlike a communicative strategy, communicative tactics is primarily related not to a communicative goal - the global concept of verbal communication, but to a set of communicative intentions that depend on various factors.

Since communicative strategies are implemented in speech actions and are associated with predicting the situation, their origins should be sought in motives that govern human activity, i.e., communicative strategies as a type of human activity have a deep connection with the motives that govern the speech behavior of a person, and a clear, observable connection with his needs and desires. The transformation of a motive into a motive-goal, the choice of one of several goals, the allocation of intermediate goals are the basis of the mechanism of communicative strategies. Two types of basic goals can be distinguished, which reflect the essential motives of human behavior. Firstly, this is the desire to be effective (that is, to realize the intention), and secondly, the need to adapt to the situation. On this basis, primary and secondary goals are identified.

The implicatures of communication are connected with the linguistic content of the utterance only indirectly. They allow the speaker to realize his communicative intention without resorting to verbal expression of what the listener can deduce from the direct meaning of the utterance. They also explain how the "speaker's meaning" can include more than the literal meaning of the sentence (indirect speech acts), how it can deviate from the literal meaning (metaphor) or even be opposite to it (irony).

They are derived from the content of the sentence, but owe their existence to the fact that the participants in the speech act are bound by a common goal of communicative cooperation. As you can see, a significant part of understanding is not related to linguistic rules that assign a certain meaning to a sentence based on the meaning of its components, but to our ability to draw conclusions

about the speaker's real intention, which does not coincide with what is literally "said."

A perlocutionary act is understood as the result of the impact that a given statement has on the addressee. This does not mean the fact that the addressee understands the meaning of the statement, but those changes in the state or behavior of the addressee that are the result of this understanding. A certain statement, or requirement, or question can change the addressee's stock of knowledge, can irritate or amuse him, scare him, make him do something.

So, making a speech act, the speaker in a certain way affects the interlocutor, while realizing his own specific communicative intention with a specific purpose. In each speech act, its locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary stages are realized.

Consider the outside of a speech act. The main components of the external side of the speech act were called by Aristotle, who laid the foundations of rhetoric and identified three components in speech: the speaker, the subject of discussion and the person to whom the speaker addresses.

As for the components of the external structure of a speech act and their number, there is no consensus among linguists either. On the basis of existing research, from three to twelve components are usually distinguished in a speech act, among them: 1) the sender; 2) the recipient; 3) the source material of the utterance (presupposition of the speakers); 4) the purpose of the message; 5) context and situation of communication.

The most significant of them are: 1) purpose; 2) the direction of the correspondence between expression and reality; 3) the inner state of the speaker; 4) features of the propositional content of a speech act; 5) the connection of a speech act with extra-linguistic establishments or institutions. Taking into account these parameters, the entire set of illocutionary acts was divided by J. Searle into five main classes: 1) representations, 2) directives, 3) commissions, 4) expressive 5) declarations.

In the theory of speech acts, a distinction is made between direct and indirect acts. In direct acts of speech, the illocutionary effect is predetermined by the direct meaning of the utterance. In indirect acts of speech, this effect does not correspond to the direct meaning of the utterance, but is conditioned by the background knowledge (presupposition) of the speakers, the conditions of communication.

Differentiation of direct and indirect speech acts and the corresponding direct and indirect statements leads to the need to distinguish between the

proper and pragmatic meaning of linguistic units. Their own meaning follows from the general linguistic meaning of the components of the utterance. The pragmatic meaning is reflected in the functional orientation of the statement. The distinction between proper and pragmatic meaning is especially important for "speech words", indicators of various aspects of a speech act. The study of speech indicators is important in an interlingual comparative plan, since different languages can use different means to express the same pragmatic meaning.

These means can be both explicit and implicit. In the works of P. Grice, mechanisms of speech implication are developed. According to his theory, the information transmitted in a speech act is divided into two parts. What is really said, and what is said, that is, is the logical content of the statement. For all the rest of the information that can be extracted by the listener from a particular utterance, the term "implicature" is introduced. Implicatures are divided into two types - conventional (presuppositions) and non-conventional (communication implicatures).

Conventional implicatures include all those non-truth-related aspects of information that are conveyed by a utterance only by virtue of the meaning of the words or forms it contains. Conventional implicatures are closely related to what the proposal says.

Traditional studies of the speech act are considered to be the works of the English scientists J.R. Searle and J. Austin, who considered a speech act as a purposeful speech action performed by a certain subject of communication in relation to a certain addressee under certain conditions with a definite intention and in accordance with the principles and rules of speech behavior adopted in a given society⁶. Subsequently, such linguists as J.F. Allen and R. Perrault (1986). N.D. Arutyunova (1990). V.V. Dement'ev (1997), I.M. Kobozeva (1986).O. G. Pocheptsov (1986), A. Cohen (1990) and others.

In linguistic literature, the inner and outer sides of the speech act are distinguished. Consider the inner side of a speech act.

The inner side of the speech act consists in the delimitation of its three stages: locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary acts. A locative act is understood as the fact of pronouncing a phrase (the act of phonation), supplying the utterance with meaning and reference (the act of reference) and assigning certain properties and relations to objects (the act of predication).

An illocutionary act is understood as a speech purposeful action of a phrase, focused on the listener and implying the possible consequences of a

pronounced utterance, namely a reaction to a speech action. In the illocutionary act, the interlocutors realize the communicative intention in the implementation of the speech act. It is considered in the theoretical literature in connection with the concept of the illocutionary force of the utterance.

The illocutionary power of the utterance (illocution) is understood as the meaning put by the speaker in the utterance of the utterance, perceived and realized by the listener.

Various classifications of speech acts are built on the basis of the concept of "illocutionary act". The most widely discussed is the classification of speech acts according to their purposefulness. From this point of view, all speech acts can be divided into informative and non-informative. The most famous classification of informative illocutionary acts was constructed by the American logician and philosopher J. Searle. The basis of this classification is a group of features, which the author himself calls "the directions of differences between illocutionary acts."

Aspects of functional pragmalinguistics. Speech activity as an object of functional pragmalinguistics

Within the framework of functional pragmalinguistics, various aspects of verbal communication fall into the field of view of researchers. So, for example, the factors of generating utterances are studied, the conditions for the successful implementation of speech acts are identified, the issues of understanding the meaning put by the communicants in the utterance are discussed, the rules that determine the effective flow of speech communication are considered, the ways of interpreting utterances from the point of view of the addressee, the addressee and the audience present are investigated. In other words, various aspects of speech activity are studied, which is the object of the study of functional pragmalinguistics.

In functional pragmalinguistics, speech activity is considered as the activity of the sender of the text according to a conscious, motivated, purposeful choice of goals of influence, for the sake of which the communication was started. These goals make it possible to segment the communication process, to identify strategically significant speech units.

Awareness of primary goals stimulates the consideration of other secondary goals. The latter are derived from various motives of human activity. Since there are usually multiple ways to achieve a goal in communication, strategies are about choice. In real communication, the speaker often has more than one goal: even one motive admits several goals, and usually the behavior of

a person is conditioned by several motives. Therefore, the effectiveness of a communication strategy is assessed by achieving the maximum number of goals or depending on their hierarchy: the most desirable goals must be achieved first. The speaker at different stages determines the priority of a particular goal and accordingly adjusts his speech actions. Thus, the communication strategy controls the optimal solution of the system of problems in a flexible and locally controlled way.

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